

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART IV. HYDRIODIC ACID FOR
SIMULTANEOUS RING-CLOSURE AND REDUCTIONS :
SYNTHESIS OF ALKYL NAPHTHALENES

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New syntheses of some alkyl naphthalenes involving simultaneous ring-closure and reductions by hydriodic acid are reported.

In the synthesis of various alkyl naphthalenes, very often, a γ -aryl butyric acid, obtained through a series of reactions, is subjected to intramolecular condensation to obtain the corresponding tetralone, which in turn is reduced to yield a hydrocarbon; the latter on dehydrogenation furnishes the required naphthalene (Harvey, Heilbron and Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 423, 2537; Wilkinson, 1931, 1333; Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 140; 1933, 16, 314; 1936, 19, 370; Barnett and Sanders, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 434; Rapson and Short, *ibid.*, 1933, 128; Brunner and Grof, *Monatsh.*, 1934, 64, 28; Sukh Dev and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 38 *et seq.*). Sometimes the final production of the aryl butyric acid is preceded by the reduction of the corresponding $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated acid, obtained by the action of alkyl magnesium halide on methyl β -aroyl-propionate.

A method has now been developed which completes all the three steps, viz. reduction, ring-closure and further reduction, in one operation.

During the synthesis of 1:3:6-trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (3-methylcadalene) (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 70) γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ -dimethylvinylacetic acid was subjected to reduction with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus. It was observed that besides the normal reduction product, γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ -dimethylbutyric acid, a neutral fraction was always obtained. The amount of this neutral fraction depended on the time for which the reaction mixture had been refluxed. In one instance (40 hours' refluxing) this formed the chief product (75%). On analysis, the neutral fraction was found to consist of 2:4:7-trimethyltetralone-1 (50%) and 1:3:6-trimethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (50%). Further work on this observation was taken up in order to work out conditions under which satisfactory yields of the tetrahydronaphthalene should be obtained. This has been accomplished.

A few not very dissimilar instances are recorded in the literature. Thus Ullmann (*Annalen*, 1896, 291, 19) obtained dihydroanthracene by the reduction of *o*-benzoylbenzoic acid with HI and red phosphorus. α -Tetralone was identified by Miescher and Billeter (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1939, 22, 605) as a minor product of the reduction of β -benzoylpropionic acid with potassium iodide and red phosphorus in syrupy phosphoric acid. Scholl and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1398; 1936, 69, 707) used acetic anhydride containing hydriodic acid in the preparation of anthranil acetates from some *o*-arylbenzoic acids.

A number of experiments were carried out on γ -(*p*-tolyl) butyric acid, using hydriodic acid and red phosphorus, and Miescher and Billeter's modification (*loc. cit.*) of the hydriodic acid reduction. Best results are obtained by heating the butyric acid with iodine and red phosphorus in syrupy phosphoric acid for 48 to 60 hours in an oil-bath

at 160°-170°. 6-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene was obtained in yields of 70 to 75%. The method was then applied to a number of other butyric acids and good results were obtained. γ -Aryl-butyric acids with a methyl radical in the α -position give better results. This may, in part, be due to the effect of the methyl group on the cyclisation of the acid (Mayer and Stamm, *Ber.*, 1923, **56**, 1424).

The reaction proceeds in a straight forward manner. The butyric acid first undergoes cyclisation to give the tetralone, which in turn is reduced to the hydrocarbon. In the case of the corresponding vinylacetic acids, the unsaturated acid is first lactonised under the influence of the acids; the lactone ring is then broken up by hydriodic acid producing the butyric acid. For example, when γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ -methylvinylacetic acid (I) is subjected to this treatment, the reaction takes the following course :

The different products of the reaction can be isolated at different stages. By refluxing (I) with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus for 3 hours at 130°-140° the lactone (II) can be isolated in yields of 65-75%, which is known to produce the butyric acid (III) on reduction with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus (Rupe and Steinbach, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 585). The acid (III) can give rise to (IV) and (V) in varying amounts depending on the time for which the reaction is to be carried out. By a prolonged treatment, (V), practically free from the tetralone, can be produced. The mechanism of the ring-closure is obscure, may be it is a case of simple dehydration.

Though the reaction has the disadvantage of requiring a comparatively long period of refluxing, this is readily counterbalanced by the simplicity of the reaction, no special attention being necessary. Moreover, the overall yields are better and the hydrocarbon is produced in a more or less pure state. Practically no coloured byproducts and resins are produced.

The method has been applied to the synthesis of a number of known alkyl naphthalenes.

1-Ethyl-6-methylnaphthalene (X).—The hydrocarbon has been synthesised previously by Brunner and Grof (*loc. cit.*). Their starting material was *p*-methylpropiophenone,

which was converted into the naphthalene after nine steps. The present scheme is outlined below.

γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ -ethylvinylacetic acid (VIII) was generated from ethyl β -(*p*-toluy)-propionate (VII) by the action of ethyl magnesium bromide (Sukh Dev, this *issue*, p. 315). This acid on treatment according to the present method gave 6-methyl-4-ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IX). The hydrocarbon on dehydrogenation with sulphur furnished the naphthalene (X).

1:3:8-Trimethylnaphthalene (XIV).— γ -(2-*m*-Xylyl)- γ -methylvinylacetic acid (XII) was prepared from β -(2-*m*-xyloyl)-propionic acid (XI) by the method of Sukh Dev (*loc. cit.*). The unsaturated acid on treatment with iodine and red phosphorus in syrupy phosphoric acid furnished the tetrahydronaphthalene (XIII), which on dehydrogenation with sulphur gave the compound (XIV).

Heilbron and Wilkinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2537) had prepared this hydrocarbon starting from 2 : 4-dimethylacetophenone by a procedure involving ten steps.

1 : 3 : 6-Trimethylnaphthalene (XVIII).— γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ -dimethylvinylacetic acid (XVI) was synthesised from methyl β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionate (XV) by the action of methyl magnesium iodide (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*). The 1 : 3 : 6-trimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (XVII) was obtained in 80% yield by the action of iodine and red phosphorus in syrupy phosphoric acid on (XVI). The hydrocarbon was then dehydrogenated to (XVIII) by sulphur. 1 : 3 : 6-Trimethylnaphthalene has been prepared previously by Ruzicka and Ehmänn (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 154) from 4-methylacetophenone.

All the hydrocarbons have been characterised by preparation of suitable derivatives, their melting points are recorded in the table, below ; the values as given in the literature are shown in parenthesis.

TABLE I

Naphthalene.	Picrate, m. p.	Styphnate, m. p.
1. β -Methyl-	117° (115°)*, 117°-17.3°**	—
2. 1 : 6-Dimethyl-	114-15° (114°)†	—
3. 1-Ethyl-6-methyl-	82° (81.5°)††	—
4. 1 : 3 : 8-Trimethyl-	125°-26° (125°)‡	—
5. 1 : 3 : 6-Trimethyl-	115° (115°)‡‡	126° (126°)‡‡

* Meyer and Fricke, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2770 ; Meyer and Meyer, *Ber.*, 1919, 52, 1251.

** Oliver and Wit, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1938, 67, 92

† Weissgerber and Kruber, *Ber.*, 1919, 52, 349.

†† Brunner and Grof, *Monatsh.*, 1934, 64, 33.

‡ Heilbron and Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2542.

‡‡ Ruzicka and Ehmänn, *loc. cit.*

Ruzicka has given a melting point of 148° on page 155, while in a table on page 142, he gives 126° as the melting point of the styphnate.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

β-Methylnaphthalene

6-Methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—*γ*-(*p*-Tolyl)butyric acid (5.0 g.), syrupy phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 15 c. c.), iodine (2.0 g.) and red phosphorus (5 g.) were heated together in an oil-bath at 160°-170° under reflux for 48 to 60 hours. The mixture was then cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether several times. The ether extract was washed twice with dilute sodium carbonate solution (some unreacted acid may be recovered from the alkaline extract), once with a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite to remove any free iodine, and finally with water. The extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. A practically colourless, mobile liquid with a characteristic smell was left. This was purified by distillation in vacuum, b. p. 98°/10 mm., yield 2.8 to 3.1 g. (70-75%)

β-Methylnaphthalene.—The above hydrocarbon (2.0 g) was heated with sulphur (0.9 g.) in a metal-bath. The reaction started at 230° with a vigorous evolution of hydrogen sulphide. The temperature was maintained at 230°-240° for ½ hour and then raised to 250°-260° and maintained there for another 15 minutes, when the evolution of hydrogen sulphide had practically ceased. The product was isolated in the usual manner and distilled over sodium as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 94°/4 mm., yield 1.5 g. (75%). The product crystallised out slowly and it was recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 34°. Oliver and Wit (*loc. cit.*) give m. p. 34.5°.

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from ethyl alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 117°.

1 : 6-Dimethylnaphthalene

γ-(*p*-Tolyl)-*γ*-methylvinylacetic acid (I) was prepared by the action of methyl magnesium iodide on ethyl *β*-(*p*-tolyl)-propionate by following the details for a similar reaction (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.* cf. Rupe and Steinbach, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 584). The product melting at 86-87° was obtained in 75% yield.

Lactone (II) of the above Acid.—*γ*-(*p*-Tolyl)-*γ*-methylisocrotonic acid (10.0 g.) was refluxed with hydriodic acid (50 g.) and red phosphorus (5.0 g) in an oil-bath at 130°-140° for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner. The crude lactone was obtained as an oil, which solidified on long keeping in a vacuum desiccator, yield 65-75%. The product crystallised from light petrol in prisms, m. p. 52° (cf. Rupe and Steinbach, *loc. cit.*).

1 : 6-Dimethylnaphthalene.—*γ*-(*p*-Tolyl)-*γ*-methylisocrotonic acid (1 part), syrupy phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 3 parts by volume), iodine (0.5 part) and red phosphorus (1 part) were refluxed together in an oil-bath at 160°-170° for 50 to 60 hours. The mixture was then worked up as described under *β*-methylnaphthalene. The crude product was obtained in a yield of 70 to 75% and was free from any tetralone as shown by the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent.

The tetrahydro derivative was dehydrogenated with sulphur as described above and purified by distillation over sodium as colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 120°/10 mm.

The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol in deep orange needles, m. p. 114-15°.

Other Alkyl Naphthalenes

β-Unsaturated acids (VIII, XII and XVI) were obtained by the action of alkyl magnesium halide on the methyl *β*-aroyl-propionates. (For details see the references quoted).

Tetrahydronaphthalenes (IX, XIII and XVII).—The reaction was carried out as described under 1:6-dimethylnaphthalene. 1-Ethyl-6-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IX) was obtained as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 118°/6 mm., yield 70.0%. (Brunner and Grof, *loc. cit.* give b. p. 126°/10 mm.)

1:6:8-Trimethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (XIII) was obtained in a yield of 65-75%, b. p. 125-126°/9 mm. (Heilbron and Wilkinson, *loc. cit.* give b. p. 133°-136°/18.5 mm.)

1:3:6-Trimethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (XVII), b. p. 110°-114°/5 mm. was isolated in a yield of 80%.

Naphthalenes (X, XIV and XVIII).—The above tetrahydronaphthalenes were dehydrogenated with sulphur, as described under *β*-methylnaphthalene. The hydrocarbons were purified by distillation over sodium and characterised by the preparation of suitable derivatives. All derivatives were recrystallised till the melting points could not be raised further. The melting points of these derivatives, as recorded in the literature, are given in Table I.

1-Ethyl-6-methylnaphthalene (X) was obtained as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 118°/4 mm. Brunner and Grof (*loc. cit.*) give b. p. 135°-138°/12 mm. The picrate crystallised from alcohol in small, silky, yellow needles, m. p. 82°.

1:3:8-Trimethylnaphthalene (XII) crystallised from alcohol in plates, m. p. 47-48°. Heilbron and Wilkinson (*loc. cit.*) give m. p. 48°. The picrate was obtained as deep orange needles from alcohol, m. p. 125-26°.

1:3:6-Trimethylnaphthalene (XVIII) b. p. 115°-120°/3 mm. was obtained in a yield of 75%. Ruzicka and Ehmman (*loc. cit.*) give b. p. 140°-144°/10 mm. The picrate crystallised from alcohol in orange-red needles, m. p. 115°. The styphnate was obtained as yellow silky needles, m. p. 126°.

The author's thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Guha for the kind interest he has shown in the work.

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Received April 10, 1948.